

History of Portuguese Colonialism in Goa as reflected in the Works and Letters of the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Centuries

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ABSTRACT

The title of the present paper literally means ‘*History of Portuguese Colonialism in Goa as reflected in the Works and Letters of the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Centuries.*’ Through this paper I intend to present the glimpses of Portuguese Colonialism in Goa and its effects on the contemporary socio-religious scenario and the responses from the subjugated natives, clergymen, vassals, emissaries, neighbouring rulers, etc. While doing so this paper also discusses the contribution of the most revered archivist historian of Goa, Dr. Pissurlencar and explores his studies and findings related to the history of colonial Goa.

Key Words: Portuguese colonialism, Native response, Narrative subversion, Interpreting the subjugation, Authoring the negotiation.

Introduction:

Dr. Panduranga Pissurlencar worked brilliantly in various positions towards achieving one common goal of preserving and reconstructing the history of Goa. Being well-versed in Marathi, Konkani, English and Portuguese languages and having finest acumen required for a historian, he unearthed histories of both pre-colonial and colonial times of Goa and also its neighbouring states. He was the director of *Arquivo Histórico do Estado da Índia* since 1931, social correspondent of the *Academia das Ciências de Lisboa* and *Academia Portuguesa da História*. And he was also the voting member of the *Centro de Estudos Histórico Ultramarinos*.¹ More than three decades of service under the colonial masters did not deter him from working unbiased. In fact, his service made sure the working conditions at the Archives and allied departments are better and suitable for objective research.

Apart from being the author of several books and articles, editing and translating several historical documents, he was also a great collector of historical works authored by several historians from both Goa and Portugal. Goa University at present hosts the priceless collection useful for the Indo-Portuguese studies in its library, donated by Dr. Pissurlencar.

O Oriente Português was a journal published by the *Comissão de Arqueologia da Índia Portuguesa*. This journal mentions that Panduranga Pissurlencar was part of the *Comissão Permanente de Arqueologia* and A B Braganca Pereira used to be its President at the time. This journal was published around 1903 and then we again hear about its restart with the initiative of the Governor General Craveiro Lopes (Portaria of the 10th October 1931).²

So, Pissurlencar, Braganza Pereira and others took its restart as an opportunity for bringing to light the history that was clouded by the Portuguese censorship and destruction of the local literary and historical works written in the Konkani and Marathi origin.

In the absence of the native historical writings what Pissurlencar could lay his hands on was a corpus of innumerable letters and correspondences between various neighbouring rulers, vassals, and the Portuguese colonial authorities at Goa. These letters between the indigenous rulers of linguas Indica and the speakers of Portuguese language necessitated the emergence of a new class of clergy men, scribes, interpreters/translators, and envoys from

among the natives equipped with the knowledge of Portuguese language and soon developed their own networks in this trade of diplomacy.

Os Escrivãos:

In Portuguese language *Escrivãos* (or *Escrivães*) literally meant those who write and in bureaucratic/administrative usage it meant the clerks. The clerks in Goa usually used to belong to the Brahmin community even during the pre-colonial period and this practice continued during the times of the Portuguese rule too as they used to be the educated and were the first among those who picked up the ways of the new regime, though there were occasional exemptions to this.

Os Enviados e Línguas do Estado:

As the envoys and the Interpreters/translators few Goans earned remarkable fame and recognition from the Portuguese government as well as from the neighbouring rulers in India. Pissurlencar not only mentioned their names but also informed about their contribution and achievements in the field of diplomacy and diplomatic relations.

Azu Naique and Crisna Sinai both were the *Línguas do Estado*. That is, official interpreters/translators and they also dispersed the duties of the *Enviados do Governo Português* (Envoys of Portuguese Government). Azu Naique was sent as envoy by the Vice-Roy of Portuguese Estado da India in the year of 1613 to northern parts of India and later to deal with negotiations with a few key officials of the Mughal emperor.³ Crisna Sinai was sent to Bijapur in the year of 1646 by the Vice-Roy Dom Filipe de Mascarenhas to obtain information but with a caution.⁴

There was a mention of yet another envoy who led the diplomatic mission in 1630 during the time of the Vice-Roy Conde de Linhares.⁵ But his name could not be found.

Conversions resulting in Mass-Migrations:

Ramogi Sinai Cotthari (Ramoji Sinai Kotthari), son of Santu Sinai, served the Portuguese government from 1645 to 1674 A.D. He was sent as an emissary to several rulers of Karnataka and Bijapur. He was also sent to the Moghuls, to the court of Shivaji and others.⁶ He was originally from Quelossim of the Salcete of the old conquests' region. But he

moved out to the Bicholim province which was at that time outside the Portuguese suzerainty. It was under the control of Bijapur. The reason could well be the ongoing conversions of the Goan Hindus into Christianity under the Portuguese rule. Several Hindus migrated or self-exiled into the territories of the neighbouring rulers those days as they were not willing to leave their dharma for some alien religion.⁷ Pissurlencar quotes Khafi Khan's observation regarding this in *Muntakhab-ul-Lubab* about the forcible conversions as the 'greatest act of Portuguese tyranny'.⁸

Angela Barreto Xavier too mentions about the migration or forced exile of the Goan Hindus of old conquests areas including the villages of Cortalim and Quelossim of Salcete to the neighbouring territories to escape the conversions and that how some of these migrants established themselves in the courts and other elite positions of the neighbouring and distant rulers.⁹ Particularly from among the Shenvis or Sinays of Brahmin community who rose to the ranks in the courts of Bijapur, Deccan and other places.¹⁰ Pissurlencar's work *Assuntos do Concelho do Estado* have references to one Apagi Sinay (1633 A.D.), the interpreter of Vitola Sinay. Vitola Sinay was the ambassador of Queledi Virabadar Naique of Equeri (Virabhadra Naique of Ikkeri)¹¹

Pissurlencar mentions various ordinances issued by the colonial rulers for Christianising the native population. D. Sebastião ordered in 1559 that all the Hindu orphan children (those who do not have parents and even grand-parents) must be taken over by the Judge of the Orphans and baptize them at the College of S. Paulo and indoctrinate them.¹² This rule was re-iterated but got the age of the children was limited to 14 years old. Accordingly, only those orphans of 14 or less than that will be taken for baptizing. So, when the Portuguese colonial rulers needed Ramogi Sinai Cotthari's services, they had to amend certain orders issued by them previously which affected the Goan Hindus adversely.¹³

Fr. Antonio Sequeira, of the company of Jesus (Jesuits), was the *Pae dos Cristãos* (Father of Christians). He managed a provision passed by the viceroy Dom Filipe de Mascarenhas, on October 13, 1646 confirming that, in case of the son of the infidel upon the death of his father, was to be declared as orphan even though his mother, grand-parents and other relatives might still be alive.¹⁴ And these children were to be taught the principles of Christianity and to be baptized even when there is no consent given by their mothers or other close relatives.

This provision was passed saying that it was based on decree number 13 that was passed in the First Provincial Council of Goa organized in the year of 1567.¹⁵ In the year of 1671, the then viceroy, Luis de Mendoça Furtado in his response to a royal order admitted that these forcible conversions of the orphan children led many natives of the Portuguese Estado da India migrate to the neighbouring territories, particularly to English Bombay.¹⁶

Loyalty to the Portuguese and Redemption from their laws:

Using this provision as a shield, the fathers of Christians took away many children who lost their fathers and put them in the residences of the catechumens in order to get them converted. This made several Hindu families to fled to the neighbouring territories under the Muslim rule.¹⁷ Kotthari's family too left their native place in Salcete to live in Bicholim in the middle of the seventeenth century because of such persecutive laws. But the interim governors Francisco de Melo de Castro and Antonio de Sousa Coutinho were in dire need of his services. So, they have got one provision passed exclusively for him on 3rd January, 1659 that he along with his family can live in the Portuguese territory without being subjected to the above discussed imposing law.¹⁸

This special provision was sent for the royal approval to Lisbon which was accepted in 1663 and Kotthari along with his family was allowed to use this provision. But the King ordered the Governors to refrain from making such provisions further for anyone else because this may prove to be detrimental for establishing Christianity in Estado da India.¹⁹

The Viceroy Antonio Melo de Castro himself was accused of being the persecutor of the Holy Office for allowing this provision coming to exist and had to ask for its immediate cancellation on January 12, 1664, as it was contradictory to the previous orders and also because it may create a scandal at Rome. It was expressed that Kotthari could have been paid generously rather than offering him this provision.²⁰

Though no information related to the decision of the government at the Metropolis could be found but Pissurlencar found a petition by Kotthari in the year of 1665, asking for the payments due to him for the services he rendered as a Chief Broker of the Customs for three years starting from 1662 to the beginning of 1665. This petition was admitted and granted in favour of him on 12th February 1665 and mentions the tenure and other details of his services rendered for the government of the Estado da India till 1665.²¹

Ramoji Sinai Kotthari was definitely one of the trusted envoys of his time for the Portuguese colonial government. His ways of working and his loyalty earned him the fame that some governors and viceroys of India were made by Kotthari. The interim governors Francisco de Melo de Castro and António de Sousa Coutinho on December 2, 1658, wrote about him that he was known for his loyalty and having his affections entrusted on Portuguese nation, he had been working and assisting the colonial government as the official interpreter and also as an envoy during the times of war and to the court of Bijapur and helped in restoring peace on several occasions.²²

In another letter dated 18th December 1659 they have again wrote about him as a loyal Brahmin who lives at Dicholim but still assist the government of Estado da India and many times went to Karnataka along with Gonçalo Martins in times of war and was several times sent by the Vice-Roys as an envoy to Bijapur.²³ Pissurlencar gives details of several letters that further talk about the contribution of Ramoji Sinai Kotthari for the success of several diplomatic missions of the Portuguese.

Duly Honoured for the Diplomacy to Ensure Peace:

Coming to the 18th Century, Bahugan Kamat Wagh was mentioned as a ‘State Translator’ by V T Gune in the introduction of *Bassein Campaign (1723 – 1741), Vol. I, Selections from Marathi (Modi) Records from Goa Archives*.²⁴ This work contains a letter written by Pandurang Vishram to ‘*Akhandith Lakshmi Alankrit Rajamanya, Rajasree Bahugun Kamat Lingua de Estado*’.²⁵ This addressing shows the kind of honour Bahugan Kamat Wagh possessed due to his position as ‘Lingua de Estado’ and also due to his accomplishments in that position. He was one of the state translators that accompanied Antonio Carneiro Alcasva and Zoje Padre Mãos during the peace treaty between the Portuguese and the Marathas (1739 A. D.).²⁶

The Lingua de Estado with the Coração de Hindu:

In the 18th Century again, there was one more interpreter/envoy who earned remarkable fame among the circles of Portuguese authority in Estado da India. But other than his diplomatic successes there was something else that earned him a unique position not only of his times but in the eyes of distinguished historians like Pissurlencar.

In the year of 1812, *Academia das Ciências de Lisboa* had published two treaties or works in the first volume of the *Colecção de notícias para a história e Geografia das nações ultramarinas, que vivem nos domínios Portugueses*.²⁷ The authors of these two works were unknown and hence published as the works of the unanimous. Some of the academicians tried to find their authors and Coronel Francisco Maria Esteves Pereira, a well-known orientalist, proposed that these two works along with one more work that came to light in 1922, were all written by one person and that is, Father Fernão de Queiroz.²⁸

Fr. Queiroz authored a book titled *Conquista Temporal e Espiritual de Ceilão* in the year of 1687 and he was in Goa the next year.²⁹ So, this fact might as well supported the presumptions of Coronel Francisco Maria Esteves Pereira about his authorship of those three works of unanimous authorship. Pissurlencar had different views regarding the authorship of these treaties. The titles of these works are as followed;

1. Breve Relação das Escrituras dos Gentios da India Oriental, e dos seus Costumes.
2. Noticia Summaria do Gentilismo da Asia.
3. Traducção em summa do Livro, que os Gentios chamão Bagavota Guita.³⁰

The first work was about the scriptures and customs of the Hindus of India and the second one was about the indigenous people of the Asia. The word ‘Gentios’ was used to for the native people of indigenous culture and religion (Pagans, Heathens), basically for the non-Christians of the colonized nations. The third one was a summary translation of Bhagawat Gita into Portuguese language.

Pissurlencar was apprehensive about the very fact that it was a task next to impossible for any non-Hindu to bring out the essence of the Hindu scriptures and translating Bhagawat-Gita in the given period of time. He carefully scrutinized the events mentioned in the *Breve Relação das Escrituras dos Gentios da India Oriental, e dos seus Costumes* and the author’s reference that this work was written after 16 years of the said events, and basing on the other reference to the death of Chandra Rao More, of Zauli (Jaavali) in the hands of Shivaji (1656 A.D.) which was contemporaneous to the previous events, he decodes that this work is written in the year of 1672, that is, after 16 years after More’s demise.³¹

He also points out to the fact that the conquests Cholia, Colle and Ramnagara by Shivaji took place in the same year (1672 A.D.) as was mentioned in the text. So, these incidents took place much before the visit of Fr. Queiroz.³² Coming to the next two works, he finds several events and descriptions common in both the works. In *Notícia Summaria do Gentilismo* and *Traducção em summa do Bagavota Guita* one historical event was hinted was that of battle of Panipat (1761) and the loss of Marathas in the hands of the Mughals.³³ Both the mention of the same event and the style of describing the event makes it obvious that the author of these two texts was one and the same. The battle of Panipat took place in 1761 much after the death of Fr. Queiroz.³⁴ That is how Pissurlencar puts an end to the speculation about the Fr. Queiroz's authorship of the three texts.

Coming to the second text again, this work also mentions how the British became masters of the territory from Prayaga to Bengal post de battle of Buxar (1764). There is also a reference to Peshwa Balaji Baji Rao.³⁵ Besides this, while the first text contains derogatory references to the Hindu divinities, the second and third texts have no such disrespectful references such as abusing the trinity, hate for idol-worship, calling the customs and traditions as superstition.³⁶

Besides, the text, *Notícia Summaria do Gentilismo da Asia* contains a verse in Sanskrit which is similar to what the Brahmins usually recite. And this verse is offered to a God who is worshipped as Ananta, who has thousand names (Sahastranama) and so on, much like God Vishnu whose Sahasranamas all Vaishnavite Brahmins chant every day.³⁷ Thus, making it evident that this text was written by a Brahmin and certainly not a Catholic. Pissurlencar by shedding light on these details proved that it was written by a Hindu and most probably a Brahmin well-versed in both Sanskrit and Portuguese languages. Since both this text and the third, the translation of Bhagawat Gita doesn't have any references later than the second half of the 18th Century makes it obvious that the author might very much belonged to the 18th Century and might have written during the times of Inquisition in Goa.

This quest for the author ends with Pissurlencar finding these texts conserved at the Biblioteca Publica de Evora and having a look at the *Notícia Summaria do Gentilismo da Asia*. And he finds that this work contains the letter of Ananta Camotim Vaga (Ananta Kamat Wagh) signed and dated 22nd February 1779, thus, clearing all the doubts about its authorship.³⁸

The Author of Subversion in times of Inquisition:

This entire research for finding the author of these texts by Pissurlencar raise a few questions as to why these texts and their author had so much importance for this archivist? That is because these two works by Ananta Camotim Vaga made him the first Goan Hindu author in Portuguese language. His deep knowledge of contemporary political events, elite and ruling personalities and geographical details reflected in his works show that he had access to the higher authorities and ruling clans. He was the *lingua do Estado* (1752 – 1793) and as such had access to the first-hand information about the dynamic political situations of his times.³⁹ And his knowledge of Portuguese language enabled him to write texts in the language of his masters. But what he chose to write is what makes him special among the scribes and authors of his times.

Both his works, *Notícia Summaria do Gentilismo da Asia* and *Traducção em summa do Livro, que os Gentios chamão Bagavota Guita* are about the native religion, scriptures and customs. During the times when the sword of Inquisition was hanging on every neck of the ‘faithful’ and the authorities were pushing the religion of the only true God in every possible measure, Ananta was introducing the native religion and beliefs to the Lusitanian world in their own language. The choice of the language is very consciously done as the Portuguese Estado da India would not allow any writings in the languages of the colonized, that is, Marathi and Konkani. Thus, he might be the *Lingua de Estado* but with a *Coração de Hindu* (that is with a ‘Heart of a Hindu’).

Conclusion:

Dr. Pissurlencar’s quest as a historian led the diplomatic and other correspondences preserved by the Portuguese colonial regime which proved to be the wonderful treasure for him to reconstruct the history of Goa. Basing on these letters exchanged by the Portuguese with the neighbouring states and vassals and the native Goans he could bring to light the networks of scribes, interpreters and envoys that effectively controlled and accomplished the diplomatic relations of the Portuguese Estado da India with its neighbours. They could in fact made Portuguese authorities to mend their rules in order to accommodate them, (of course due to the necessity of the colonial empire) and also were led to the changes in the attitude of the Portuguese towards allowing Hindus to practice their customs and traditions, the

Kotthari's case for example., and also later due to the conditions laid by the Bhonsles to allow the status quo in the region of *novas conquistas* (New Conquests) led the Portuguese to loosen up their strategy of enforced conversions. The determination with which Ananta Kamotim Vaga subverted the colonial repression by authoring two texts in Portuguese language in times of Inquisition shows that the new class of the Interpreters/Envoys emerged was determined to retain and assertive to continue their native religion and customs, and while working for the colonial masters their purpose was safeguarding the interests of the natives as well or to say in other words, they could slowly but surely established themselves in a position that can not be substituted by the so-called fidalgos (Men of noble origin and customs) of European origin.

End Notes:

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21. Ibid.,

22. Ibid., p. 5.

23. Ibid., pp. 8 – 46.

24. Gune, V. T. ed. *Bassein Campaign (1723 – 1741), Vol. I, Selections from Marathi (Modi) Records from Goa Archives*, Panaji: Publication of Historical Archives of Goa, 1979, p. 3.

25. Ibid., p. 55, See letter No: 79.

26. Ibid., p. 3.

27. Pissurlencar, Panduranga. *Um Hindu, Autor Desconhecido de Duas Publicações Portuguesas*, Lisboa: Academia Das Ciências De Lisboa, 1959, p. 3.

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31. Ibid., pp. 3, 4.

32. Ibid., p. 4.

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34. Ibid.,

35. Ibid.,

36. Ibid., p. 5.

37. Ibid.,

38. Ibid., pp. 6, 7.

39. Ibid., p. 6.